

1 Rlf, a zinc finger nuclear factor associated with genomic stability and exhaustion.

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7 We describe here transcriptional properties of Rlf, a zinc finger nuclear factor associated with genomic
8 stability and exhaustion. In BRCA1 mutant human mammary gland organoids, Rlf was silenced. In
9 humans with lung cancer, Rlf activation was dependent on p53 mutational status *in vivo*. In vitro, small
10 hairpin depletion of p53 in human mammary epithelial cells resulted in activation of Rlf. We and others
11 have described an intrinsic association of genomic stability with the exhaustion program; TIGIT is a
12 cardinal cell surface marker associated with exhaustion. When comparing total transcription between
13 natural killer cells fractionated based on level of TIGIT expression (TIGIT^{hi} and TIGIT^{lo}), Rlf was silenced in
14 the TIGIT^{hi} fraction. Rlf expression is controlled during transformation and associated with genomic
15 instability. Genomic instability and exhaustion are likely precisely transcriptionally co-modulated.

16 Citations

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